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LXII INTERNATIONAL CORRESPONDENCE SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE
**EUROPEAN RESEARCH: INNOVATION IN SCIENCE,
EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGY**

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LXII INTERNATIONAL CORRESPONDENCE SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE «EUROPEAN RESEARCH: INNOVATION IN SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGY»

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THE ROLE OF LEGAL EDUCATION AND CUSTOMS AND TRADITIONS AND ETHICS OF PILGRIMAGE IN IMPROVING YOUTH'S MORALE AND TO COUNTERING THREATS

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Abstract: this article highlights the need to fight through the education, training, ancient traditions, traditions and values of all kinds of threats against youth morality, which is now one of the most pressing issues. In perspective on the present schools, the primary issue is the deficiency of talented and significant educational staff, despite the fact that the material and specialized base of the schools is given. This thusly, will influence the training and childhood of youngsters. Hence, the infringement of morals, morals and conduct is the consequence of our deficient academic impact on young people, who are frequently hard to raise. The adolescent's indecent conduct is described by deficiencies in family, school and legitimate instruction. Outside likewise assume a significant job in the arrangement of a youngster. The way to building up an individual's character and mental self view is managing.

Keywords: spiritual life, legal education, tradition, pilgrimage, national consciousness, education.

РОЛЬ ПРАВОВОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ И ТРАДИЦИЙ, РИТУАЛОВ И ПАЛОМНИЧЕСТВА В ПРОДВИЖЕНИИ МОРАЛЬНОГО ДУХА МОЛОДЕЖИ И ПРОТИВОДЕЙСТВИИ УГРОЗАМ

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Аннотация: в этой статье подчеркивается необходимость образованием, обучением, древними традициями, традициями и ценностями бороться против всевозможных угроз против морали молодежи, что в настоящее время является одной из наиболее актуальных проблем. Что касается нынешних школ, то основной проблемой является дефицит

талантливых и значительных педагогических кадров, несмотря на то, что материальная и специализированная база школ дана. Таким образом, это повлияет на воспитание и детство молодежи. Следовательно, нарушение морали и поведения является следствием нашего недостаточного академического воздействия на молодых людей, которых часто трудно воспитать. Непростойное поведение подростка объясняется недостатками в семье, школе и законном обучении.

Ключевые слова: *духовная жизнь, правовое воспитание, традиции, паломничество, национальное самосознание, воспитание.*

Nowadays it isn't a secret, countering many threats is very important. For that reason today as an immediate response to this, the current legislation is required to instill the essence of anti-threat laws in educational institutions through national educators and legal education teachers and staff. It is real to concentrate that threats divide into 3 groups, they are: ideological, spiritual, information threats. But we must answer the question about "What is the threat?". Threat-the form of threats arising in the real world due to aggression of local, regional and all-region negative factors that have been targeted for a specific period of time in relation to the life and activity of the society and the state and represent an unstable social and political situation. And its representation and appearing types firstly noted in the book of the 1st president of the republic of Uzbekistan I.A.Karimov, that book's name is "Uzbekistan is on the threshold of the 21st century: security threats stability and development"[1]. Threats can be differently: internal and external, with a distance they can be near and far. The experience in Early 21st century shows us that the safety of the nation and society and its stability, its improvement, its progress depend on understanding endangered threats to this nation or society. Eliminating the sources of threat that aren't rooted, alert about threats not to let ignorance all of them noted lots of books our ancestors. In this regard we can say Abu Nasr Forobiy's point of view about "to lead the country consists of preventing and preventing the perils of the nation." [2]. Awareness of internal and external threats to our ancestors has been raised to an important level and it was very important to prevent this. In the reign of Amir Temur, all incidents focused on the need to be sufficiently aware of the social and political processes. To know and to be aware of real threats, Amir Temur gave great attention and thought as the main task to create the information system in that time. "I was aware of all of my nation's life. And I assigned one specialist to know about my every nation's life, that nation's staff, their live life, and their communications with each other and I called that specialists storyteller" said in "Rules of Temur" [3]. Amir Temur demanded from that specialists to give information about that nation's internal and external situations and without that he thought this position can give guarantee to the security of that country or the nation and he offered to give attention dividing the money to the right ways and the security and progress of that nation and country.

Our great ancestors have been trying to understand the nature of the demands of society. At the same time, the analysis of the internal factors that lead of the emergence of the threat situation. The conclusions drawn are important in their activities. In particular, attention was paid to the soundness of public policy and its adherence to the principles of the time. It is well known that due to the difficult situation in the world the structure of the spiritual and ideological threat factor covers political, economic, social, cultural and spiritual spheres of life. After gaining independence, care for the physical and spiritual development of the younger generation has been identified as one of the main priorities. In addition it is recommended that children be taught science at an early age. "If you have a son- says Adurbada's advice- give him to school since childhood, because reading is the light of the eye" [4].

In view of today's schools, the main problem is the shortage of skilled and profound pedagogical staff, even though the material and technical base of the schools is provided. This in turn, will affect the education and upbringing of young people. Therefore, the violation of ethics, ethics and behavior is the result of our inadequate pedagogical influence on adolescents, who are often difficult to bring up. The teenager's immoral behavior is characterized by shortcomings in family, school and legal education. Outdoors also play a major role in the formation of a teenager. The key to developing a person's identity and self-image is dealing. In schools where educational

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любого случайного реципиента в зависимости от типа коммуникации и мотива создания» [2, с. 25]. Данное направление хип-хопа зародилось и продолжает существовать как противоправное деяние, но следует отметить, что с популяризацией субкультуры проводятся официальные соревнования, конкурсы данного направления уличного искусства. Следует отметить, что некоторые государственные или муниципальные структуры дают официальные разрешения на деятельность райтеров (авторов граффити), например в рамках благоустройства городской территории, спортивных площадок и т.п. Существует практика найма коммерческими организациями представителей направления для нанесения граффити.

Представители хип-хопа выделяют такое направление субкультуры как «знание» или «философия Хип-хопа». Ими выдвигаются такие тезисы как: «саморазвитие и постоянное обучение с помощью старших товарищей, любая дуальность и конфронтация в культуре может быть только полевой и шуточной, одна любовь к Хип-хопу может объединять враждующие народы и даже страны, при грамотной интерпретации». Следует отметить, что не все представители хип-хопа поддерживают вышеуказанные тезисы, выражая противоположные положения в своем творчестве.

Рассмотрев основные направления хип-хопа, мы вернемся к истории развития творческой составляющей данной субкультуры. В конце 80-х начале 90-х появляются новые жанры музыкально-исполнительского направления хип-хопа, такие как: гангста-рэп, джи-фанк, джаз-рэп, рэп-рок (альтернативная музыка) и другие. Рэп исполнители в данный период обращаются к афроцентристским и политическим темам, также в текстах прослеживается тематика насилия и употребления наркотиков. С развитием цифровых музыкальных инструментов и возможностей звуковой аппаратуры хип-хоп исполнители применяют в своем творчестве «сэмпловость». В США начинается творческая конкуренция между хип-хоп представителями западного и восточного побережий страны, которое положительно повлияло на развитие хип-хоп культуры в плане творчества. Средства массовой информации определили данный период как золотой век хип-хопа.

Отметим, что творческие разногласия между восточным побережьем и западным переходили в криминальные ситуации (перестрелки, убийства, нападения и т.д.). Отражение данной действительности мы находим в творчестве, например появляется такой жанр как «beef», который представляет из себя музыкальные композиции под названием «diss», содержащие оскорбления и негативное отношение к оппоненту. После убийства известного представителя субкультуры Тупака Шакура между враждующими сторонами было подписано мировое соглашение, согласно которому проводятся совместные концертные туры представителей обоих побережий. Хип-хоп артисты начинают зарабатывать деньги на своем творчестве, строить бизнес.

С началом нового тысячелетия хип-хоп вливается в общую культуру. На концертных площадках вместе с артистами эстрады выступают рэп-артисты, проводятся международные официальные конкурсы граффити, брейк-данс становится дисциплиной олимпийских игр и т. д. Следует отметить, что не все современные представители хип-хоп культуры коммерциализируют свое творчество. Они считают, что хип-хоп – это философия жизни, то есть следует жить согласно тезисам «философии хип-хопа». Например, один из родоначальников русскоязычного рэпа Владислав Валов (Sheff) назвал одну из своих композиций «Rap music ради дела, а не ради денег».

Вышесказанное позволяет утверждать, что хип-хоп, зародившись на улице в криминальных районах городов США как оппозиционное движение, считавшихся в то время маргинальных групп населения, в итоге стал частью общей культуры. Отметим, что в настоящее время ученые социологи, историки, философы, культурологи, искусствоведы, психологи изучают хип-хоп культуру с научной точки зрения. Следовательно, если творчество становится популярным, одобренным обществом, законным, актуальным для изучения науки его следует считать частью господствующей культуры.

work is failing, adolescents are more, likely to be influenced by street groups and different groups on the Internet, including the popular culture that has become a pressing problem today. It is worth saying that young people behave in the street on the basis of iodine culture, and when they go to the shrines, they do not even have the understanding of etiquette of pilgrimage. Adolescents have a strong tendency to play; for them the rules of the game become a pattern of behavior. Adolescents forget about the rules of self-evaluation. As a result, traits such as hooliganism, cruelty, disobedience and indifference will appear. In addition, young people are becoming increasingly disrespectful not only of the etiquette of pilgrimage, but also of our customs and rituals, which are symbols of our own identity. One of the requirements for teachers today is to properly explain and promote them the deeper meaning, of our customs and traditions, and to develop a sense of behavior in pilgrimages. Article 5 of the Law on Education, approved at the 9th session of the Supreme Soviet of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 29, 1997, provides for the right to engage in pedagogical activity. According to him, persons with the appropriate education, professional training and high moral qualities have the right to engage in pedagogical activity. Requirement of teaching staff in higher education institutions carried out on a competitive basis in accordance with the Regulation approved by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Persons prohibited from carrying out pedagogical activity by the court, are not allowed to engage in educational activities. The main purpose of education is to create spiritually rich individuals with independent scientific thinking and problem solving skills. As society grows, so does the demand of life. Therefore, as the scope of scientific knowledge grows and the level of science grows, the need for logical thinking and problem solving becomes more intense. From this point of view, we conclude that the education system should work not only in the light of today's needs, but also in defining and estimating future needs. Because today's youth will be the cornerstone of the future society. This means that the education system should prepare the students for the future, not the present. This is also one of the features of education. In view of all of the above, in order to improve the pedagogical activities in the organization of educational work among young people and the prevention of crime and offenses, it is necessary to:

1. To pay special attention to the allocation of separate classrooms for the promotion of legal knowledge in secondary schools.

2. On the basis of the subject "The idea of national independence and the basics of spirituality", the customs formed under the motto "From national revival, to national development", have introduced a new discipline "Discipline", which reflects who we really are and our national mentality and modernity, reach.

3. Formation of IT (international technology) classes in schools and kindergartens for the purpose of continuous learning, dissemination and wide application of advanced knowledge.

Rational use of the accumulated knowledge and pedagogical experience is the key to their effective implementation of education and upbringing of skills of regular observance of laws and regulations of our state.

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be highly educated. Because human's physical abilities (strength, quickness, flexibility, activeness and toleraseness), technique and tactical, spiritual features are very complex pedagogical process. The sport coach must know his students every aspect of life condition whose has friends are, participating in social activities, studying process and his family life. Therefore the coach must be many sided person. The coach must know the participants health the development of their physical abilities and temper features, their mind and others. The coach must have a pedagogical diary in order to write his students temper features and their behavior. 570 In this way the coach archives high results with his students it is important to make good relationship with students. Pedagogical experiments are based on respecting students personality and demanding great achievements demanding and respecting are vital parts of the educating process in other hand, there are some unrespecting situation found in physical education activity by teachers. This kind of situation is the fault of the teacher mis conducting education process. Consequently, children do not offend sport activities then they commit bad activities. Pedagogical uncial is based on being sincerity, kindness and talking politely. The attitude of the coach during the competition should be good. The sportsman must be trained in the competition as well. But sometimes they need physiological help. The coach must give them necessary instructions. Un like other coaches a good coach must support his students when they don't achieve their goals. The coach is respected if the behaves like this. The coaches success is organizing and holding sport competitions and activities. The typical features of physical education are making high mood, supporting fun and activities among the participants in the team. Feeling the world happy, makes the students be sure their strength. Children come over difficulties when doing physical exercises and it helps them to be have persistence and sincere. Team exercises serve to more social activeness.

Used literature:

of their life. The pedagogical skill of the specialist of physical education appears with organizing fundamental and special branches of teaching programs, knowing physical training and instructions, popular sport games and sport regencies. The specialist of physical education brings up not only physical ability of the participant but also spiritual view of the participants and helps to choose their direction and human duties in their life. Pedagogic skill has many sides as an educational process. Pedagogical skill appears in the specialist of physical trainer with affective teaching and development their physical ability, their spiritual outlook, organizing sport teams of the students, their individual features. The sincerity and truth fullness of the trainer affect positively on the development of spiritual view of the children. Children try to act as their trainer. The negative behavior of the trainer affects badly. Because children mostly take up not their verbal instructions but their acts. That's why the specialist of physical training must be educated morally and aesthetically with up to date standards. We must spend out strength and time making our nation stronger, more intelligent cleverer and hopper than us. The spiritual education helps us in this way. If we lose in this issue and neglect our sacred custom we will get out of world wide developing way. The coach must be experienced. Education is a very complex process and in order to be true trainer the special lost of physical training must be well educated and do his job forth fully. And he must do the following principles: - providing educational and training process according to educational standards; - individual features of the participants according to their age (physiologic and mental features); - respecting and encoring the participants; - organing the educational process in "cheerful mood"; - providing the educational effects with pedagogical demands; - organing the lessons and the process of training based on new pedagogical cal and information technology method. The trainer must give attention to the participants spiritual condition and prepare them future hope and work in society. Sport is not essential only for victory but it also increases the spiritual features of the sports ment. Achieving higher level in sport the coach must

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THE ROLE OF SPORT AND THE TRAINER IN THE EDUCATION OF PERFEKT GENERATION

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Annotation: This article deals with the problems of the developing of the culture of greeting and preparing higher qualified sportsmen and the demands to the specialist of physical education.

Key words: physical education specialist, coach, sport, pedagogical demands, process of training, trainers, culture of greeting, controlling education process features.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются проблемы развития культуры приветствия и подготовки спортсменов высшей квалификации и требования к специалисту по физическому воспитанию.

Ключевые слова: специалист по физическому воспитанию, тренер, спорт, педагогические требования, процесс обучения, тренеры, культура приветствия, управление особенностями учебного процесса.

Physical education it is a pedagogical process, based on morphologic and functional development of human body, and deals with the essential movement skills